

THE ADHESION OF CARBON FIBERS TO THERMOPLASTIC POLYMERS

W.D. Bascom,
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
University of Utah
Salt Lake City, UT 84112

and

R. M. Jensen and L. W. Corder
Graphite Fibers Development
Hercules Inc.
Magna, UT 84044

ABSTRACT

The bond strength between fiber and matrix critically effects the performance of fiber reinforced composites. However, the factors that determine fiber/matrix adhesion are complex and not thoroughly understood. In this paper experiments on the adhesion of carbon fibers to thermosetting and thermoplastic composites are described. Two different fiber types were studied which exhibit the same bond strength to epoxy polymers but very different bond strengths to thermoplastics. Surface chemical analysis of the different fibers using ESCA and contact angle measurements did not provide an unequivocal explanation for the difference in adhesion. These analyses did reveal the fiber surfaces to be very chemically heterogeneous.

INTRODUCTION

It has been said that, "the interface is the heart of a composite"(1). Certainly, the utility of fiber reinforced composites as structural materials depends in a very fundamental sense on the stress transfer and thus the adhesion between the fiber and matrix. This deceptively simple process is actually very complex and is discussed in every textbook on fibrous composites and in numerous research papers. However, the great majority of this literature deals with the theory of stress transfer with relatively little supporting experimental evidence.

The bond strength between fiber and matrix has been studied experimentally using the embedded single fiber tensile test. This bond strength determines the level of stress transfer into the fiber before mechanical continuity is lost. The analysis for stress transfer into a single filament from a large volume of matrix was first developed by Cox (2) and later modified by Kelly and Tyson(3). Experimental studies using this

technique to investigate polymer matrix/fiber stress transfer and adhesion were pioneered by Fraser et al (4,5) for glass fibers and by Drzal et al (6,7) for carbon fibers.

In this report some observations are presented on single carbon filaments embedded in thermoplastic polymers and the results compared with earlier work (8) with the same fibers in epoxy matrix polymers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The specimen configuration is shown schematically in Fig. 1 for determining the bond strength of a single carbon filament to an epoxy polymer. It is made by positioning the filament in a polysiloxane rubber mold, filling the mold with the liquid epoxy and then oven curing the assembly.

Figure 1. Schematic of a single filament embedded in a micro-dogbone of polymer

Figure 2 - Micro-tensile test device

The specimen is mounted in a micro-tensile test machine (Fig.2) and the machine placed on the stage of a light microscope. If the epoxy is transparent and stress birefringent then the fragmentation of the filament can be observed and, by viewing between crossed polarizing filters, stress birefringence patterns near broken fiber ends can also be viewed. In a typical experiment, the filament fragments until a critical length is reached, L_c , below which the stress transfer is less than the fiber tensile strength, σ_f . No further fiber breakage occurs when the stress on the specimen is increased.

The birefringence patterns that develop at fiber breaks as stress is applied to a specimen are shown in Figure 3. Note the nodes that initially develop at fiber breaks (Fig. 3A) and that these nodes recede from the break as the stress is increased leaving a more or less uniform sheath of birefringence around the fiber (Fig 3B).

Figure 3 - Stress birefringence patterns at breaks in a single filament viewed between crossed polarizing filters.

A different specimen configuration was used to study carbon fibers in thermoplastic polymers. As shown in Fig.4, a single filament was placed lengthwise on a narrow bar (12.5mm x 6.25mm x 37.5mm) of the polymer and then coated with a solution of the same polymer in a low boiling solvent.

Figure 4 - Schematic of single filament embedded in a coating of thermoplastic polymer.

The fiber was embedded to a depth of at least two fiber diameters which was determined to be sufficient to prevent any effect of the upper surface of the coating on fiber fragmentation. Drying conditions were established for complete removal of the solvent for each solvent-polymer combination. The drying temperature was never allowed to exceed 85°C. Higher temperatures produced significant residual thermal (radial) compressive stresses (9).

The only experimental parameter measured in these studies was the critical length which was found to exhibit a broad statistical distribution. For a single specimen the coefficient of variation was typically 25-40. Consequently, at least ten specimens were tested for each fiber-polymer pair and the critical length data combined and statistically analysed for the mean value, standard deviation, 99% confidence on the mean, and other statistical parameters. Various statistical analyses were used, normal, log-normal and Weibull, but the calculated parameters did not differ significantly. All of the results reported here were obtained using normal statistical analysis. In Fig. 5 the histogram and normal overlay are shown for a typical carbon fiber-epoxy system.

Figure 5 - Histogram and normal overlay for combined ζ data from ten specimens.

RESULTS

Carbon Fiber-Epoxy Systems

The designation and pertinent properties of the carbon fibers are listed in Table 1 and the epoxy resins are listed in Table 2. The mean critical aspect ratios, ζ_c/d , for the carbon fibers in different epoxys are presented Table 3 along with the 99% confidence limits. The fiber diameter, d , was assumed to be constant although this is not strictly true. However the variation is small compared to the variation in ζ_c and therefore disregarded for present purposes. Some of the fibers had been sized with epoxy compatible sizings.

TABLE 1

Properties of Carbon Fibers

Fiber designation	Diameter d , μm	0° Laminate Tensile Properties		
		Strength ksi/MPa	Modulus Msi/GPa	Elongation %
AS1*	8.0	450/3103	33/228	1.32
AS4*	6.84	520/3587	34/235	1.53
AS6*	5.52	600/4173	35/243	1.65
IM6*	5.20	635/4378	40/278	1.50
XAS**	6.64	500/3447	33/230	1.67

* Hercules Inc.

** Grafil Hysol

TABLE 2
Properties of Epoxy Polymers

Designation	Epoxy	Curing agent	Tensile Properties	
			Strength ksi/MPa	Modulus ksi/MPa
828/m-PDA	Shell 828 (DGEBA)	metaphenylene diamine	5.8/40	523/3620
828/D230	Shell 828 (DGEBA)	Jeffamine D230 (polyoxypropylene amine)	9.3/64	379/2614
55A*	DGEBA	diamine	12.6/87	430/2966

DGEBA = diglycidylether of bisphenol A

* Hercules proprietary resin

TABLE 3
Critical Aspect Ratio for Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Systems

Carbon Fiber	Epoxy	Critical Aspect Ratio, l/d	
		mean	99% confidence limits on the mean
AS1	828/mPDA	42*	-----
AS4	828/mPDA	55	53 - 57
AS4	828/D230	60	58 - 62
AS4W**	828/mPDA	57	55 - 59
AS4W	55A	57	55 - 59
AS6G	828/m-PDA	76	73 - 79
AS6G	828/D230	73	71 - 76
IM6G	828/m-PDA	84	81 - 88
IM6G	828/D230	80	78 - 83
XAS	828/m-PDA	32	31 - 33

* Reference 6

** G and W are epoxy compatible sizings

The data in Table 3 indicate a systematic increase in l_c/d from AS1 to IM6. Moreover, it was found that the critical aspect ratio data for these fibers could be reasonably correlated with the unidirectional laminate tensile strength of the different fibers in the same epoxy matrix (Hercules 3501-5A) as shown in Fig. 6. Included in Fig 6 are the data for Hercules AS-1 reported by Drzal(5). This correlation should be viewed with considerable caution. The micromechanics of 0° laminate failure are far more complex than the failure of embedded single filaments. However, by keeping the matrix resin the same as well as fiber volume and other variables, the laminate strength does provide a relative measure of the fiber strength, σ_f . The linear relation between fiber strength and the critical aspect ratio in Fig 6 requires that the boundary shear strength, τ , is essentially constant for these fibers in 828/m-PDA or that the differences are small compared to the differences in fiber strength.

Figure 6 - Correlation of l_c/d with 0° tensile strength; AS1◇, AS4●, AS6○,IM6○

The birefringence patterns observed at fiber breaks for the carbon fibers in epoxy polymers (Fig 3) change spontaneously when the stress on the specimen is released. As shown in Fig 7, the initial nodes disappear but the sheath of birefringence that formed when the nodes receded from the fiber breaks persists.

Figure 7 - The birefringence that persists after removing the tension on a single filament specimen. Compare with Fig. 3

Carbon Fiber-Thermoplastic Systems

A study was made of the critical length of carbon fibers in thermoplastic polymers using the specimen configuration shown in Fig 4. The polymers studied are listed in Table 4 along with the solvent used to apply the polymer film, the drying conditions to remove the solvent, and the pertinent mechanical properties. Critical lengths for AS4 in the various polymers are listed in Table 5. It is immediately obvious from this data that the critical length for AS4 in all of the thermoplastics is considerably greater than for the same fiber in epoxy polymers (Table 3).

TABLE 4

Mechanical Properties of the Thermoplastic Polymers
and the Conditions Used to Form the Specimen

Polymer	Solvent	Drying Conditions (time/temperature)	Tensile Properties	
			strength ksi/MPa	modulus ksi/MPa
polycarbonate	methylene chloride	24hr/25°C 8hr/75°C	9.5/65	345/2400
polyphenylene oxide	methylene chloride/dichloro- ethane, 1/1 wt. ratio	4hr/25°C 16hr/81°C	7.0/48	325/2200
polyetherimide*	methylene chloride	24hr/25°C 8hr/75°C	15.2/105	430/2965
polystyrene/ polyphenylene oxide (25/75 wt. ratio)	methylene chloride/dichloro- ethane, 1/1 wt. ratio	4hr/25°C 24hr/81°C	-----	-----

*Ultem, General Electric Corp.

TABLE 5

Critical Aspect Ratio for AS4 in Thermoplastic Polymers

Matrix	Critical Aspect Ratio, ℓ/d	
	mean	99% confidence limits on the mean
polycarbonate	108	101-115
polyphenylene oxide	121	115-125
polyetherimide	93	90-96

The birefringence pattern exhibited by AS4 in the thermoplastics also differed significantly from the pattern observed for the epoxy specimens. This difference is illustrated in Fig 8 for AS4 in polycarbonate. The birefringent nodes appeared at a fiber break but then immediately receded away from the break leaving only a weak sometimes barely visible sheath of birefringence around the fiber. This behavior can best be described as an interfacial "unzipping" of the matrix from the fiber. On removing the stress on the specimen, essentially all of the birefringence disappeared. This behavior is distinctly different from the epoxy matrix specimens where a sensible stress was required to cause the initial nodes to recede from the breaks and in doing so left a strongly birefringent sheath that persisted when tension was removed.

Figure 8 - Birefringence patterns at a break in a carbon fiber in polycarbonate.

Similar tests were conducted on the XAS and AS1 fibers and the critical aspect ratios are listed in Table 6. The XAS critical aspect ratios were significantly lower in the thermoplastic than for AS4 (Table 4) and AS1. Infact, they are comparable to the values obtained in an epoxy (Table 3).

TABLE 6
Critical Aspect Ratios for XAS and AS1 Fibers in Thermoplastic Polymers

Fiber	Polymer	Critical Aspect Ratio, l_c/d	
		mean	99% Confidence on the mean
XAS	polycarbonate	54	52-56
XAS	polyphenylene oxide	55	52-56
XAS	polyetherimide	55	52-57
XAS	polystyrene/polyphenylene oxide (25/75 wt. ratio)	61	58-64
AS1	polycarbonate	119	114-124
AS1	polyetherimide	84	80-88

The XAS and AS4 fibers differ in mechanical properties (Table 1) and also in surface roughness as shown in Fig. 9. The AS4 is essentially smooth whereas the XAS is highly striated. However, the Hercules AS1 is also highly striated (Fig 9). Critical aspect ratios are given for AS1 in Table 6 and are comparable to the values obtained for AS4 in the same polymers. Evidently, the difference in the surface roughness between AS4 and XAS does not account for the difference in critical lengths of the two fiber types in thermoplastics.

A

B

C

1
μm

Figure 9 Scanning electron microscopy photographs of AS4 (A), XAS (B) and AS1 (C)

DISCUSSION

The relation between the boundary shear strength, τ , the fiber tensile strength, σ_f , and diameter, d , developed by Kelly and Tyson (3) is,

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f}{2} \left(\frac{d}{l_c} \right)$$

For purposes of later discussion it is useful to rearrange this equation to show the dependence of the critical aspect ratio on σ_f and τ ,

$$\frac{l_c}{d} = \frac{\sigma_f}{2\tau}$$

The boundary shear strength is determined by the shear yield strength of the matrix polymer or by the interfacial adhesion between fiber and matrix. In the case of the carbon fiber-epoxy systems studied here it has been argued that stress transfer is limited by the shear yield strength of the matrix. This conclusion is based on shear yielding of the matrix near fiber breaks i. e., Figure 3. However, this yielding could be the result of the thermally induced radial compressive stress on the fiber (reference 9). Drzal (6) has presented evidence that stress transfer is limited by the adhesion strength between fiber and matrix and not by matrix yield strength. Neither case is unequivocally established (8).

The results presented in Figure 6 for the carbon fiber-epoxy specimens suggest that for the systems studied the interphase shear strength, τ_c , is essentially constant so that l_c/d is determined by the fiber strength, i.e., Eq. 2. The critical aspect ratio of AS4 was essentially constant for different epoxy matrices and fiber sizings (Table 3 and reference 8) and the correlation between fiber strength and the critical aspect ratio (Fig 6) support this argument. However, the data for XAS do not fit this correlation.

In distinct contrast, the results for AS4 in the thermoplastics strongly indicate low interfacial strength. The critical lengths were nearly twice that obtained for the same fiber in the epoxys which from Eq. 2 implies a low value for τ . Moreover, the unzipping behavior of the birefringence patterns observed for all of the

AS4/thermoplastic systems is characteristic of interfacial failure and the fact that the receding nodes did not leave a birefringent sheath around the fiber indicates no detectable shear yielding of the matrix.

On the other hand, the XAS fiber exhibited good adhesion to all the thermoplastics as well as the epoxys. The difference could not be explained by the highly striated surface of the XAS compared to the smooth AS4 since the ASI is also striated yet exhibited poor adhesion to the thermoplastics.

Various attempts were made to improve the adhesion of AS4 to the thermoplastics ; different sizing agents, different levels of surface treatment, and heat cleaning of the fiber at temperatures up to 700°C to remove surface volatiles. None of these treatments were successful.

In an effort to explain the difference in the behavior of the AS4 and XAS , surface analyses using ESCA were conducted. The results suggested a slightly higher surface oxygen level on the XAS but the difference was within the normal variation between fiber lots.

Wettability measurements were made on the two fiber types using a Wilhelmy balance tensiometer. The wetting liquids included water, hexadecane, α - bromo-naphthalene and diiodomethane. No clear cut differences were observed in the wettability of the fibers.

However, the contact angle measurements and also the ESCA results indicated that all of the carbon fiber surfaces are very chemically heterogeneous. For example, the advancing water contact angle on AS4 ranged from 57° to 70° between individual samples of fiber and for a given sample oscillated 10° along a length of 10mm of fiber. These studies are still in progress and the results will be reported in detail in a later publication.

CONCLUSIONS

The critical length values and the birefringence patterns observed for all of the carbon fibers tested in an amine-cured bisphenol A diepoxide indicate that stress transfer is limited by the shear yielding of the matrix near the fiber/epoxy boundary although interfacial failure cannot be ruled out.

In distinct contrast, two of the carbon fibers (AS4 and AS1) exhibited poor adhesion to thermoplastic polymers whereas XAS exhibited good adhesion to the same thermoplastics. Efforts to modify the surface of AS4 to improve adhesion to the thermoplastics by sizing agents, surface treatment variations and heat cleaning were unsuccessful. Surface analysis of the AS4 and the XAS by surface spectroscopy and wettability measurements did not reveal any differences that would explain the difference in adhesion to the thermoplastics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research was funded by Hercules Inc., Magna Ut. and by the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. The authors wish to thank Mr. John Weidner and Mr. Neil Hansen, Hercules Inc. and Dr. Jeffery Hinkley and Dr. Norman J. Johnston, NASA Langley Research Center for their help and advice during the course of this work.

REFERENCES

1. Piggott, M. R., Sanadi, A., Chua, P. S., and Andison, D., "Mechanical Interactions in the Interphasial Region of Fibre Reinforced Thermosets". In Composite Interfaces, H. Ishida and J. L. Koenig, Eds., North-Holland, New York, 1986, pp. 109
2. H.L. Cox, "The Elasticity and Strength of Paper and other Fibrous Materials." Brit. J. Appl. Phys., 3 (1952) 72
3. A. Kelly and W.R.V. Tyson, "Tensile Properties of Fibre-reinforced Metals: Copper/Tungsten and Copper/Molybdenum," Mech. & Phys. of Solids 13 (1965) 329
4. W. A. Fraser, F.H. Ancker and A. T. DiBenedetto, "A Computer Modeled, Single Filament Technique for Measuring Coupling and Sizing Agent Effects in Fiber Reinforced Composites," Proc. Conf. on Reinforced Plastics, SPI, 1975, Section 22A, 1
5. W.A. Fraser, F.H. Ancker, A.T. DiBenedetto and B. Elbirli, Evaluation of Surface Treatments for Fibers in Composite Materials," Polym. Comp., 4(1983) 238

6. L.T. Drzal, M.J. Rich and P.F. Lloyd, "Adhesion of Graphite Fibers to Epoxy Matrices: I, The Role of Fiber Surface Treatment," J. Adhesion, 16 (1982), 1
7. L.T. Drzal, M.J. Rich, M.F. Koenig and P.F. Lloyd, "Adhesion of Graphite Fibers to Epoxy Matrices; II, Effect of Fiber Finish," J. Adhesion, 16 (1983) 133
8. W.D. Bascom and R.M. Jensen, "Stress Transfer in Single Fiber/Resin Tensile Tests," J. Adhesion, 19 (1986) 219
9. J.M. Whitney and L.T. Drzal, "Three Dimensional Stress Distribution Around an Isolated Fiber Fragment," TOUGH COMPOSITES, ASTM Special Technical Publication, Philadelphia, PA, in press